

Exploring the effect of different cosmologies on the Epoch of Reionization 21-cm signal with POLAR

Anshuman Acharya^{1*}, Qing-bo Ma^{2,3}, Sambit K. Giri⁴, Benedetta Ciardi¹, Raghunath Ghara⁵, Garrelt Mellema⁶, Saleem Zaroubi^{7,8}, Ian Hothi^{9,10}, Ilian T. Iliev¹¹, Léon V. E. Koopmans⁷, Michele Bianco¹²

¹Max-Planck-Institut für Astrophysik, Garching 85748, Germany

²School of Physics and Electronic Science, Guizhou Normal University, Guiyang 550001, PR China

³Guizhou Provincial Key Laboratory of Radio Astronomy and Data Processing, Guizhou Normal University, Guiyang 550001, PR China

⁴Nordita, KTH Royal Institute of Technology and Stockholm University, Hannes Alfvéns väg 12, SE-106 91 Stockholm, Sweden

⁵Department of Physical Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Kolkata, Mohanpur, WB 741 246, India

⁶The Oskar Klein Centre, Department of Astronomy, Stockholm University, AlbaNova, SE-10691 Stockholm, Sweden

⁷Kapteyn Astronomical Institute, University of Groningen, P.O. Box 800, 9700AV Groningen, The Netherlands

⁸Astrophysics Research Centre of the Open University of Israel, Ra'anana 4353701, Israel

⁹LERMA, Observatoire de Paris, PSL Research University, CNRS, Sorbonne Université, F-75014 Paris, France

¹⁰Laboratoire de Physique de l'ENS, ENS, Université PSL, CNRS, Sorbonne Université, Université Paris Cité, 75005, Paris, France

¹¹Astronomy Centre, Department of Physics & Astronomy, Pevensey III Building, University of Sussex, Falmer, Brighton, BN1 9QH, United Kingdom

¹²Institute for Particle Physics and Astrophysics, ETH Zurich, Wolfgang-Pauli-Str 27, 8093 Zurich, Switzerland

Accepted XXX. Received YYY; in original form ZZZ.

ABSTRACT

A detection of the 21-cm signal power spectrum from the Epoch of Reionization is imminent, thanks to consistent advancements from telescopes such as LOFAR, MWA, and HERA, along with the development of SKA. In light of this progress, it is crucial to expand the parameter space of simulations used to infer astrophysical properties from this signal. In this work, we explore the role of cosmological parameters such as the Hubble constant H_0 and the matter clustering amplitude σ_8 , whose values as provided by measurements at different redshifts are in tension. We run N -body simulations using GADGET-4, and post-process them with the reionization simulation code POLAR, that uses L-GALAXIES to include galaxy formation and evolution properties and GRIZZLY to execute 1-D radiative transfer of ionizing photons in the intergalactic medium (IGM). We compare our results with the latest JWST observations and explore which astrophysical properties for different cosmologies are necessary to match the observed UV luminosity functions at redshifts $z = 10$ and 9 . Additionally, we explore the impact of these parameters on the observed 21-cm signal power spectrum, focusing on the redshifts within the range of LOFAR 21-cm signal observations ($z \approx 8.5 - 10$). Despite differences in cosmological and astrophysical parameters, the 21-cm power spectrum at these redshifts agrees with presently observed upper limits. This suggests the need for broader physical parameter spaces for inference modeling to account for all models that agree with observations. However, we also propose stronger constraining power by using a combination of galactic and IGM observables.

Key words: cosmology: dark ages, reionization, first stars; cosmology: theory; galaxies: formation;

1 INTRODUCTION

The Epoch of Reionization (EoR) refers to the period of the Universe when sufficient astrophysical objects formed and emitted UV photons to (re)ionize the neutral hydrogen of the intergalactic medium (IGM). One of the most important probes for studying this epoch is the brightness temperature fluctuations of the 21-cm line of neutral hydrogen (HI) as observed in emission or absorption against the Cosmic Microwave Background radiation (CMB; Field 1959; Hogan & Rees 1979; Madau et al. 1997; Shaver et al. 1999; Tozzi et al. 2000; Ciardi & Madau 2003; Zaroubi 2013). The 21-cm signal is produced

by the forbidden hyperfine spin-flip transition of the ground state of neutral hydrogen. As the excited state has an extremely long lifetime and neutral hydrogen is abundant in the IGM at the start of the EoR, this signal can be used as a tracer of the IGM ionization state. A statistical detection of the strength of the fluctuations of its brightness temperature allows us to constrain models of the Universe during this early formation stage.

For this purpose, multiple interferometric low-frequency radio telescopes have been designed to search for this signal, such as PA-

* E-mail: anshuman@mpa-garching.mpg.de

PER¹, MWA², HERA³, LOFAR⁴, and the upcoming SKA⁵. While the signal is yet to be detected, upper limits of the 21-cm power spectrum have been obtained and are becoming increasingly tighter (e.g., Mertens et al. 2020; Trott et al. 2020; HERA Collaboration et al. 2023; Acharya et al. 2024c). These have allowed us to rule out some extreme astrophysical models through a comparison with simulations (e.g., Ghara et al. 2020; Mondal et al. 2020; Greig et al. 2021a,b; Abdurashidova et al. 2022). New methods that utilize multi-redshift power spectrum observations (Ghara et al. 2024; Choudhury et al. 2024), wavelet statistics (Hothi et al. 2024), and simulation-based inference (Saxena et al. 2023; Greig et al. 2024) have also been developed to improve the understanding of parameters governing the properties of the IGM.

At the same time, galaxies that formed during the EoR that are responsible for HI ionization have also been studied using hydro-dynamical and/or radiative transfer simulations with different prescriptions, such as CROC (Gnedin 2014; Gnedin & Kaurov 2014; Esmerian & Gnedin 2021, 2022, 2024), FIRE (Ma et al. 2018), TECHNICALOR DAWN (Finlator et al. 2018), SPHINX (Rosdahl et al. 2018), CRASH simulations (Eide et al. 2018, 2020; Ma et al. 2021; Kostyuk et al. 2023; Basu et al. 2024), C²RAY simulations (Mellema et al. 2006; Dixon et al. 2016; Giri & Mellema 2021; Hirling et al. 2024; Giri et al. 2024), CoDA LII (Ocvirk et al. 2016, 2020), ASTRID (Bird et al. 2022), COLDSIM (Maio et al. 2022; Casavecchia et al. 2024), THESAN (Kannan et al. 2022; Garaldi et al. 2022; Smith et al. 2022; Garaldi et al. 2024), and SPICE (Bhagwat et al. 2024). Although these simulations are ideal tools to investigate the IGM and galactic properties, they are computationally expensive and thus limited in box size and/or in the number of simulations. Thus, they cannot be used for building a wide range of models for comparison with the 21-cm power spectrum or their upper limits.

To this aim, semi-numerical approaches such as SIMFAST21 (Santos et al. 2010a,b), BEARS (Thomas et al. 2009), 21cmFAST (Mesinger & Furlanetto 2007; Mesinger et al. 2011), GRIZZLY (Ghara et al. 2015, 2018), REIONYUGA (Mondal et al. 2017), ARTIST (Molaro et al. 2019), AMBER (Trac et al. 2022) and BEORN (Schaeffer et al. 2023) are typically employed. To incorporate a more realistic modeling of galactic properties into these methods, codes such as ASTRAEUS (Hutter et al. 2021), MERAXES (Mutch et al. 2016; Balu et al. 2023) and POLAR (Ma et al. 2023, hereafter M23) have been developed.

The LOFAR EoR Key Science Project (KSP) team has designed POLAR, a semi-numeric approach which strikes a balance between speed and complexity of relevant physical processes, by post-processing N -body Dark Matter (DM) simulations with Semi-Analytic Models (SAMs) of galaxy formation and evolution, and subsequently applying a 1-D radiative transfer (RT) code GRIZZLY (Ghara et al. 2015, 2018), an updated version of BEARS (Thomas et al. 2009). This allows a fast modeling of the 21-cm signal power spectrum, while at the same time accounting for important galactic properties and RT effects. Consequently, observations of the 21-cm line can also be combined with data obtained in other frequency bands (e.g. from JWST) to jointly constrain IGM and galactic properties.

Here, we investigate the impact of varying cosmological parameters whose low and high redshift measurements are in tension, i.e.,

the Hubble parameter $H_0 = 100h \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ and the matter clustering amplitude σ_8 , on the 21-cm signal at $z \approx 10.11, 9.16$, and 8.3 , i.e., the three redshifts targeted by LOFAR (Mertens et al. 2024, in prep). For this, we adopt different observed values for them to create different cosmological models. The fiducial model is taken to be that of Planck Collaboration et al. (2020) measurements of $h = 0.6766$ and $\sigma_8 = 0.8102$, while a higher h value is taken to explore the low redshift measurement of $h = 0.733$ from studies of Cepheid variables in the host galaxies of 42 Type Ia supernovae (Riess et al. 2022). Similarly, a lower σ_8 value of 0.702 is adopted from the low redshift measurement of anisotropic galaxy clustering measurement analysis (Tröster et al. 2020). Lastly, we also consider the case of a higher σ_8 of 0.88 from recent eROSITA results (Ghirardini et al. 2024) to consider both extremes of σ_8 measurement. Motivated by results obtained in the context of the 21-cm signal shown by Giri et al. (2023) and Acharya et al. (2024b), we additionally implement the Fixed & Paired (F&P) approach (Angulo & Pontzen 2016) to boost effective volumes of the simulations and suppress cosmic variance.

In Section 2, we discuss the setup of the POLAR simulations with different cosmologies used in this work. We additionally present two cases, one in which only the cosmologies differ, and one in which astrophysical parameters are also changed to match observations of UV luminosity functions (UVLFs) from HST legacy fields and JWST programs (Finkelstein et al. 2015; Bouwens et al. 2015, 2021; Harikane et al. 2022; Bouwens et al. 2023a,b; Harikane et al. 2023; Leung et al. 2023; McLeod et al. 2024; Adams et al. 2024) at $z = 10$ and 9 . In Section 3, we present the resulting galactic and IGM properties, and in Section 4, we discuss the implications of varying astrophysical and cosmological parameters for inference modeling from 21-cm signal observations, jointly constrained with other observables of the EoR. Finally, we summarize our results in Section 5.

2 METHODOLOGY

Building on M23, we utilize a similar setup by running N -body DM simulations, and then post-process them with the L-GALAXIES SAM (Barrera et al. 2023; Henriques et al. 2015, 2020) to model the formation and evolution of galaxies, and with the 1-D radiative transfer code GRIZZLY (Ghara et al. 2015, 2018) to model the gas ionization and the 21-cm signal from neutral hydrogen. In Sections 2.1 and 2.2, we highlight the key parameters used for setting up the simulations and analysis done in this work. Further, in Section 2.3 we propose two cases: one where we keep the astrophysical parameters the same for all cosmological model, and one in which we tune them to match UVLFs observed with JWST and HST at $z = 10$ and 9 . We refer to the first and second case as “unconstrained” and “constrained”, respectively.

2.1 Dark-matter simulations

We use the GADGET-4 code (Springel et al. 2021) for running N -body DM simulations with a volume of $(150h^{-1} \text{ cMpc})^3$ and 2048^3 DM particles. This translates into a DM particle mass of $5 \times 10^7 M_\odot$, matching the particle resolution of larger simulations used by the LOFAR EoR KSP team (see for example Giri et al. 2019b,a). The box size is chosen to probe wave-modes of $k \leq 1.0h \text{ cMpc}^{-1}$, where the best results from observations with LOFAR, HERA, MWA (and eventually SKA) are expected (Koopmans et al. 2015). This corresponds to box sizes $> 100h^{-1} \text{ cMpc}$ (Iliev et al. 2014), although

¹ Precision Array to Probe EoR, <http://eor.berkeley.edu>

² Murchison Widefield Array, <http://www.mwatelescope.org>

³ Hydrogen Epoch of Reionization Array, <https://reionization.org/>

⁴ Low-Frequency Array, <http://www.lofar.org>

⁵ Square Kilometre Array, <https://www.skao.int/en>

Table 1. The four N -body dark matter simulation models considered in this work. From left to right, the model name, the adopted value of h and σ_8 , and the reference for the values. All other cosmological parameters are fixed to the Planck Collaboration et al. (2020) values.

Model	h	σ_8	Reference
fiducial	0.6766	0.8102	Planck Collaboration et al. (2020)
h high	0.7330	0.8102	Riess et al. (2022)
σ_8 low	0.6766	0.7020	Tröster et al. (2020)
σ_8 high	0.6766	0.8800	Ghirardini et al. (2024)

Kaur et al. (2020) suggests box sizes of $> 175h^{-1}$ cMpc being necessary when accounting for X-ray heating of the IGM. To sidestep this issue, we assume that at our redshifts of interest, the IGM has already been heated above the CMB temperature (see Section 2.2.2). We additionally employ the F&P approach (Angulo & Pontzen 2016) to mitigate sample variance, and thus run two realisations of each DM simulation. Each pair of realisations has the mode amplitudes fixed to the square root of the initial matter power spectrum, and the phases of the second realisations (B-series) are obtained by mirroring those of the first realisations (A-series). The F&P approach of averaging observables of these two realisations has been shown to boost the statistical precision of the matter power spectrum, bispectrum and halo mass function (Angulo & Pontzen 2016; Chartier et al. 2021; Maion et al. 2022; Villaescusa-Navarro et al. 2018), Lyman- α power spectra (Anderson et al. 2019), 21-cm signal power spectrum and bispectrum (Giri et al. 2023; Acharya et al. 2024b) and several other quantities derived from simulations (Villaescusa-Navarro et al. 2018; Klypin et al. 2020). Beyond this, we use the same random seed to minimize the effect of randomized initial conditions for both the A and B-series of simulations.

For our reference simulation, we assume a “fiducial” Λ -Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) cosmological model based on Planck Collaboration et al. (2020, specifically the TT,TE,EE+lowE+lensing+BAO case), setting $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.6889$, $\Omega_m = \Omega_b + \Omega_{dm} = 0.3111$, $\Omega_b = 0.04897$, $H_0 = 100h$ km s $^{-1}$ Mpc $^{-1}$ with $h = 0.6766$, $\sigma_8 = 0.8102$ and $n_s = 0.9665$, where the symbols have their usual meaning. Further, we consider three additional cosmologies, where we vary h and σ_8 , while keeping the other parameters fixed to the above-mentioned values. This is necessary to consider the maximum impact of changing cosmological parameters across the range of observed values. First, we adopt $h = 0.7330$ (from Riess et al. 2022), and refer to this as the “ h high” model. In addition, we explore two extreme values of σ_8 , namely the “ σ_8 low” case with $\sigma_8 = 0.702$ (Tröster et al. 2020), and the “ σ_8 high” case with $\sigma_8 = 0.88$ (Ghirardini et al. 2024). The details of the four simulation models are listed in Table 1.

The initial conditions for all simulations are generated at $z = 199$ with a second-order Lagrangian perturbation theory based on the NGENIC algorithm implemented into GADGET-4, using the same linear theory power spectrum as Hernández-Aguayo et al. (2023). We generate 90 snapshots between $z = 20$ and $z = 5$, for which we save full snapshot information. However, in order to ensure a maximum step size of 10 Myrs between snapshots used to build halo merger trees with the Friend-Of-Friends (FOF) group finding algorithm (Springel et al. 2001), we perform a finer gridding to generate a total of 156 output time steps for FOF groups. We use a standard linking length of 0.2 times the mean particle spacing and a minimum group size of 64 DM particles (corresponding to a minimum halo size of $\approx 3 \times 10^9 M_\odot$). Substructures within halos are identified using the SUBFIND-HBT algorithm (Han et al. 2018;

Figure 1. Halo mass functions for our four models: fiducial (cyan), h high (red), σ_8 low (purple) and σ_8 high (green) at $z = 10$ (top panel) and 9 (bottom). The A- and B-series are shown with dashed and dotted lines, respectively. The corresponding fit for each simulation using the Tinker et al. (2008) model is shown with a solid grey line.

Springel et al. 2021). Finally, the gravitational softening length is set to 0.025 of the mean particle spacing, i.e. $\approx 1.83h^{-1}$ kpc.

To evaluate the performance of the simulations, in Figure 1 we present the halo mass function (HMF) as $M_h \frac{dn_h}{dM_h}$, where M_h and n_h are the halo mass and number density respectively, and compare them with fits by Tinker et al. (2008), computed using the Python package HMF (Murray 2014) at $z = 9$ and 10. As in this study, Tinker et al. (2008) take into account the non-universality of the HMF by considering the impact of varying the cosmological parameters in the Λ CDM model. We note that the fiducial and h high models at these redshifts produce very similar HMFs despite some noticeable differences in their corresponding fits. A deeper exploration indicates that our simulation setup is less sensitive to differences in the Hubble parameter, given the choice of the starting redshift, and that the initial conditions were generated using second-order Lagrangian perturbation theory. A significantly higher starting redshift or third/fourth-order Lagrangian perturbation theory is instead required to better match the fits. Nevertheless, deeper analysis reveals that some differences do exist especially at the extremities of the HMF, which leads to differences noted in subsequent sections. Lastly, we note that the B-series has slightly more massive halos in all models. This is purely because of the choice of the random seed, which happens to lead to some regions of massive halo formation in the B-series where the A-series have voids.

2.2 Galactic and IGM properties with POLAR

POLAR is a semi-numerical model designed to obtain high- z galaxy

properties and the 21-cm signal from the IGM in a fast and robust manner. It combines the semi-analytical galaxy formation and evolution model of L-GALAXIES (Henriques et al. 2015, 2020; Barrera et al. 2023) with the one-dimensional radiative transfer code GRIZZLY (Ghara et al. 2015, 2018).

2.2.1 Semi-Analytic modeling of galaxies

We use L-GALAXIES as described by Barrera et al. (2023), as a post-processing module of GADGET-4. This is an updated version of the publicly available L-GALAXIES 2020 that was used by M23. L-GALAXIES implements most major physical processes of gas cooling, star formation, galaxy mergers, supernovae feedback, black hole growth, AGN feedback, and dust attenuation. While Barrera et al. (2023) largely builds on Henriques et al. (2015), we also consider the parameters used by Henriques et al. (2020) before adapting them for our purposes. In particular, we focus on those that control star formation efficiency (α_{SF}), star formation efficiency during galaxy mergers ($\alpha_{\text{SF,burst}}$), AGN accretion rate (k_{AGN}), reheating of cold gas by star formation (ϵ_{reheat} , V_{reheat}), and the energy released by each supernova (E_{SN}).

We tune the parameters to match photometric observations of the UVLFs from JWST and HST at redshifts $z = 10$ and 9 , as these redshifts are observationally relevant for the LOFAR EoR KSP. We note that L-GALAXIES assumes a 100% escape fraction for the UV photons, and thus we also implement the dust attenuation approach of Henriques et al. (2015). This is a simplified model, however, we note that more complex models may lead to greater suppression of the UV luminosity function. We list all the possible parameters available in L-GALAXIES, and their values set to match UVLF observations as discussed in Section 2.3.

2.2.2 Radiative transfer and the 21-cm signal

modeling the EoR requires the inclusion of radiative transfer to describe the hydrogen ionization and heating. For this, we take the results of the N -body simulations from Section 2.1 and the semi-analytic modeling of galaxies from Section 2.2.1, and post-process them with the 1D radiative transfer code GRIZZLY, as done by M23. GRIZZLY uses pre-computed ionization and temperature profiles of gas for different source and density properties at various redshifts to model the ionization and heating processes and the differential brightness temperature of the 21-cm signal (δT_{b}).

More specifically, GRIZZLY requires as input the gridded matter density field and dark matter halo masses from the N -body simulation, as well as the corresponding galactic stellar masses and stellar ages obtained with L-GALAXIES. Our reference simulation has a grid of 256^3 cells, resulting in a cell size of $\approx 600 h^{-1}$ kpc, but we use a range of different sizes (from 64^3 to 512^3 cells) to assure convergence of output values in the range $12 > z > 5$. Next, we assume that the gas density scales by a factor of $\Omega_{\text{b}}/\Omega_{\text{dm}}$ with the dark matter density. Lastly, as done in M23, we use the Binary Population and Spectral Synthesis (BPASS; Stanway & Eldridge 2018) code to model the Spectral Energy Distributions (SEDs) of stellar sources. In future work, we will also explore the impact of other source types such as X-ray binaries, shock-heated interstellar medium, and accreting black holes (as done in Eide et al. 2018, 2020; Ma et al. 2021).

GRIZZLY computes δT_{b} as follows (see Furlanetto et al. 2006):

$$\delta T_{\text{b}} = 27x_{\text{HI}}(1 + \delta_{\text{B}}) \left(1 - \frac{T_{\text{CMB}}}{T_{\text{S}}} \right) \times \left[\left(\frac{\Omega_{\text{b}} h^2}{0.023} \right) \left(\frac{0.15}{\Omega_{\text{m}} h^2} \frac{1+z}{10} \right)^{1/2} \right] \text{mK}, \quad (1)$$

where x_{HI} is the fraction of neutral hydrogen, δ_{B} is the fractional overdensity of baryons, T_{S} is the hydrogen spin temperature, T_{CMB} is the temperature of the CMB photons at redshift z , and Ω_{m} is the total matter density. As done by M23, we assume $T_{\text{S}} \gg T_{\text{CMB}}$ which is valid when the IGM has been sufficiently heated by X-ray sources and expected to be the case during the EoR in most scenarios. Additionally, we also ignore the impact of redshift space distortions. Thus Equation 1 is reduced to

$$\delta T_{\text{b}} = 27x_{\text{HI}}(1 + \delta_{\text{B}}) \left[\left(\frac{\Omega_{\text{b}} h^2}{0.023} \right) \left(\frac{0.15}{\Omega_{\text{m}} h^2} \frac{1+z}{10} \right)^{1/2} \right] \text{mK}. \quad (2)$$

We define the power spectrum of δT_{b} as:

$$P_{21\text{cm}}(\mathbf{k}) = \delta_{\text{D}}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}') \langle \delta T_{\text{b}}(\mathbf{k}) \delta T_{\text{b}}(\mathbf{k}') \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where δ_{D} is the Dirac delta function, $\delta T_{\text{b}}(\mathbf{k})$ is the differential brightness temperature in Fourier space, and $\langle \dots \rangle$ is the ensemble average. In the following, we will report our results in terms of the normalized form of the power spectrum, given by (see Peacock 1999, for details):

$$\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2(k) = \frac{k^3}{2\pi^2} \times P_{21\text{cm}}(k). \quad (4)$$

2.3 UV luminosity functions

Because Henriques et al. (2015, 2020) tuned the L-GALAXIES parameters to the low-redshift Universe ($z < 3$), it is necessary to adapt them to match the redshift regime that we are interested in (see Vani et al. 2024, on discrepancies from observations at higher redshifts). In particular, for the LOFAR EoR KSP team, focussing on redshifts $10 > z > 8.5$ is crucial, as that's the regime in which the LOFAR telescope is most sensitive. Thus, we change the values of the parameters listed in Section 2.2.1 to match the observations of the UVLFs from HST legacy fields and JWST programs (Finkelstein et al. 2015; Bouwens et al. 2015, 2021; Harikane et al. 2022; Bouwens et al. 2023a,b; Harikane et al. 2023; Leung et al. 2023; McLeod et al. 2024; Adams et al. 2024) at $z = 10$ and 9 . We have also varied other parameters, but their impact on the UVLFs is minimal (see M23, for a detailed analysis of the impact of different parameters). In future work, we will broaden the range of astrophysical parameters and analyse their effect on other observables.

First, we tune the α_{SF} , $\alpha_{\text{SF,burst}}$, and E_{SN} values in order for the fiducial case to match the observed high- z UVLFs. Additionally, we reduce the value of the fraction of AGN formed (k_{AGN}) by a small amount, which improves the agreement at the brightest magnitudes ($M_{1600,\text{AB}} < -20$). Similarly, the supernova feedback-based heating efficiency parameters ϵ_{reheat} and V_{reheat} are changed to improve the agreement for $M_{1600,\text{AB}} > -19$.

We consider two more cases. In the first one, the same L-GALAXIES parameters of the fiducial model above are adopted for all N -body simulations, to investigate the impact of different cosmologies on the 21-cm signal but disregard observations of galaxies at high redshifts. We refer to this case as ‘‘unconstrained’’. This case allows us to have a clearer picture of the impact of changing cosmologies on the 21-cm signal, without astrophysical processes potentially cancelling out their effects on observables. In the second case, called ‘‘constrained’’,

Figure 2. Comparison of A and B-series averaged UVLFs for the unconstrained (left) and constrained (right) cases at redshifts $z = 10$ and 9 . The different colours represent different cosmological models: fiducial (cyan), h high (red), σ_8 low (purple), σ_8 high (green). We also show the dust attenuated (solid) and unattenuated (dashed) UVLFs, and JWST and HST observations (Finkelstein et al. 2015; Bouwens et al. 2015, 2021; Harikane et al. 2022; Bouwens et al. 2023a,b; Harikane et al. 2023; Leung et al. 2023; McLeod et al. 2024; Adams et al. 2024, grey circles).

Table 2. List of astrophysical parameters in L-GALAXIES (see Henriques et al. 2015, 2020, for more details) that can be tuned to control galaxy formation and evolution. We show the names of the parameters in column 1, and Henriques et al. (2015) and Henriques et al. (2020) values tuned to $z < 3$ observations in columns 2 and 3. Our cosmological models (fiducial, h high, σ_8 low and σ_8 high) tuned to UVLF observations at $z = 10$ and 9 are shown in columns 4, 5, 6 and 7 respectively. We show the parameters that differ from Henriques et al. (2015, 2020) values in bold. For the unconstrained case (see text for more details), we use the fiducial model parameters for all our N -body simulations.

Parameter	Henriques et al. (2015)	Henriques et al. (2020)	fiducial	h high	σ_8 low	σ_8 high
α_{SF}	0.025	0.060	0.20	0.20	0.50	0.20
$\alpha_{\text{SF,burst}}$	0.60	0.50	0.80	0.80	0.90	0.80
$\beta_{\text{SF,burst}}$	1.90	0.38	0.38	0.38	0.38	0.38
$k_{\text{AGN}} [10^{-3}M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}]$	5.3	2.5	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
f_{BH}	0.041	0.066	0.066	0.066	0.066	0.066
$V_{\text{BH}} [\text{km s}^{-1}]$	750	700	700	700	700	700
$M_{\text{r.p.}} [10^{14}M_{\odot}]$	1.2	5.1	5.1	5.1	5.1	5.1
$\alpha_{\text{dyn.fric.}}$	2.5	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
ϵ_{reheat}	2.6	5.6	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
$V_{\text{reheat}} [\text{km s}^{-1}]$	480	110	250	250	250	250
β_{reheat}	0.72	2.90	2.90	2.90	2.90	2.90
η_{eject}	0.62	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50	5.50
$V_{\text{eject}} [\text{km s}^{-1}]$	100	220	220	220	220	220
β_{eject}	0.8	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
$\gamma_{\text{reinc}} [10^{10} \text{ yr}^{-1}]$	3.0	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
$E_{\text{SN}} [10^{51} \text{ erg}]$	1.0	1.0	0.80	1.0	0.15	2.00
Z_{yield}	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030

the L-GALAXIES parameters are changed for each cosmological model to match the observed UVLFs. This is potentially more interesting, as it allows for a joint constraint of astrophysical and cosmological parameters based on multi-frequency observations. The L-GALAXIES parameters adopted are listed in Table 2. We show the UVLFs for the unconstrained case in Figure 2a and the constrained case in Figure 2b for all cosmological models, along with observations at $z = 10$ and 9 . In the unconstrained case, we note that the fiducial

and h high models have similar UVLFs, while the σ_8 low model underpredicts the UVLF as compared to observations. On the other hand, the σ_8 high model is mildly overpredicted. These results are in agreement with the impact of these parameters on matter clustering. In the constrained case, the boost in star formation due to higher α_{SF} and $\alpha_{\text{SF,burst}}$ values, and a lower E_{SN} value allows the σ_8 low model to match the bright end of the UVLF. However, due to lower matter clustering, it does not produce as many faint galaxies as the

other cases, and sees a steep drop at $M_{1600,AB} > -18$. On the other hand, the high E_{SN} in the σ_8 high model strongly suppresses star formation and thus matches other cosmological models and the JWST and HST observations. Additionally, it produces more faint galaxies even at $M_{1600,AB} > -16$. Between the h high and fiducial models, the difference is minimal at $z = 10$ due to the mildly higher E_{SN} in the h high model, however at $z = 9$, the impact of higher matter clustering in the h high model shows up in the form of more galaxies at the low luminosity end.

Lastly, we note that in the fiducial model, the brightest galaxy at $z = 14$ has $M_{1600,AB} = -20.36$, while at $z = 13$, it has $M_{1600,AB} = -20.60$, which is in agreement with the recent spectroscopically confirmed galaxies at $z = 14.32$ and 13.90 (Carniani et al. 2024). For completeness, in Appendix A we also show the UVLFs in the range $12 > z > 5$ for the constrained case. We find that our models reasonably agree with UVLF observations across this redshift range.

2.4 Reionization history

The final choice made while building our models is that of the escape fraction of UV photons, which is set to a value of $f_{esc} = 12.5\%$ as for this the fiducial model reionizes completely (i.e. the average neutral fraction $\langle x_{HI} \rangle$ becomes zero) by $z = 5$. The other models however may reionize completely at other redshifts.

As an example of the impact of the escape fraction, in Figure 3 we show the A-series (i.e., with “fixed” initial conditions in the F&P pair of simulations) middle slices of the δT_b cubes for the four cosmological models in the constrained case at $z = 12, 10, 8$ and 6 . We note that there are no major differences until $z = 6$. However, a closer inspection reveals larger ionized regions in the h high model at $z = 10$ as compared to the fiducial model. This is due to the impact of matter clustering. We additionally show the B-series middle slices in Appendix B.

We also calculate the average of the A and B-series volume-averaged neutral hydrogen fraction ($\langle x_{HI} \rangle$) for multiple snapshots from $z = 12$ to $z = 5$. While we have a large number of snapshots as discussed in Section 2.1, for the sake of simplicity, to run POLAR we adopt a uniform step size of $\Delta z = 0.5$. In Figure 4, we present the redshift evolution of $\langle x_{HI} \rangle$ in the unconstrained (top) and constrained (bottom) cases for all cosmological models, together with observational constraints (Fan et al. 2006; Totani et al. 2006; Ota et al. 2008; Uchi et al. 2010; Bolton et al. 2011; Dijkstra et al. 2011; McGreer et al. 2011; Mortlock et al. 2011; Ono et al. 2012; Chornock et al. 2013; Jensen et al. 2013; Robertson et al. 2013; Schroeder et al. 2013; Pentericci et al. 2014; Schenker et al. 2014; McGreer et al. 2015; Sobacchi & Mesinger 2015; Choudhury et al. 2015; Mesinger et al. 2015; Greig et al. 2017; Davies et al. 2018; Mason et al. 2018; Hoag et al. 2019; Greig et al. 2019; Jones et al. 2024, collected in the CoReCon module, Garaldi 2023). As in some models, the redshift of reionization is not properly captured due to the coarse redshift resolution, we additionally provide a fit to these curves in order for the end of reionization to be estimated more accurately.

We note that in the unconstrained case, all models reionize at different redshifts. Reionization is the fastest (at $z = 6.4$) in the σ_8 high model, as structure formation happens earlier. The σ_8 low model is still only 45% reionized by $z = 5$ because of the lack of sources, and shows the poorest agreement with observational constraints. In the constrained case, the differences are reduced, but still significant. In particular, we note that the σ_8 low model reionizes the fastest at $z = 5.75$, while the σ_8 high model is only $\approx 65\%$ ionized by $z = 5$. This reversal of reionization histories with respect to the unconstrained case is due to the impact of different astrophysical

parameters. Specifically, the significantly higher E_{SN} in the σ_8 high model blows away gas and thus suppresses star formation which consequently reduces the production of ionizing photons. On the other hand, the higher α_{SF} and $\alpha_{SF,burst}$ in the σ_8 low model along with the lower E_{SN} significantly boosts star formation.

As the four models reionize at different redshifts and the end of the EoR can be observationally constrained (e.g., detections of Gunn-Peterson troughs in the Lyman- α forest as shown in Becker et al. 2015, Qin et al. 2021 and Bosman et al. 2022), this in turn limits the choice of astrophysical and cosmological parameters. However, to model more realistically the final phases of reionization, we also need to account for the unresolved absorbers that slow down the reionization process (see Georgiev et al. 2024; Giri et al. 2024). These, though, are not included in this work. Nevertheless, we note that given the choice of $f_{esc} = 12.5\%$, the calculated optical depth to reionization for the fiducial model is in agreement with *Planck* observations.

We additionally show the reionization history and the evolution of the 21-cm signal power spectrum across redshift for the fiducial model with $f_{esc} = 25\%$ in Appendix C to show the impact of the choice of f_{esc} .

3 RESULTS

In this section, we present the results from our simulations with respect to various galactic and IGM properties for the unconstrained and constrained case. To reduce the effect of cosmic variance, we always consider the A and B-series averages when comparing to observations.

3.1 Unconstrained case

In the unconstrained case, we follow the galactic and IGM observables for models with the UVLFs reported in Figure 2a.

3.1.1 Galactic properties

In Figure 5a, we show the mass-binned star formation rate (SFR) of galaxies in the four models at $z = 10$ and 9 . The solid lines refer to the median SFR, with the shaded regions referring to the 16th to 84th percentiles. The star formation main sequence (SFMS) in each case is additionally compared with results from various recent JWST programs (Treu et al. 2023; Fujimoto et al. 2023; Looser et al. 2023; Bouwens et al. 2023b; Papovich et al. 2023; Arrabal Haro et al. 2023b,a; Long et al. 2023; Leethochawalit et al. 2023; Atek et al. 2023; Robertson et al. 2023; Heintz et al. 2023a,b; Jin et al. 2023; Helton et al. 2024; Jung et al. 2024) represented by grey circles with a binning of ± 0.25 around the redshift. As all parameters affecting the star formation rate were kept the same across all four models, we note that the overall trends match, and agree, with observations. The impact of matter clustering is seen at the low-mass end, where greater matter clustering allows the formation of a statistically significant sample of smaller mass galaxies in the σ_8 high and h high models, while the smallest mass galaxies formed in the σ_8 low case are an order of magnitude more massive. Further, at the high mass end, we note that the σ_8 high model produces the most massive galaxies which also have the highest SFR.

To confirm the agreement in star formation rates, in Figure 6a we additionally look at the global star formation efficiency (SFE) at the same redshifts, defined as the ratio of the stellar and halo mass scaled by $f_b = \Omega_b/\Omega_m$, i.e. $M_{star}/M_{halo}f_b$, as a function of the halo

Figure 3. Maps of δT_b of the A-series middle slices for the four cosmological models in the constrained case at $z = 12, 10, 8,$ and 6 (from top to bottom). Here the darkest regions represent the ionized regions with $\delta T_b = 0$. Note that δT_b cannot assume negative values, due to the assumption of $T_S \gg T_{\text{CMB}}$.

mass M_{halo} . We also compare this to Spitzer observations at $z = 7$ (Stefanon et al. 2021) and to abundance matching estimates from Tacchella et al. (2018). As mentioned above, the parameters controlling the star formation efficiency are the same across all models, and thus the corresponding global SFE is the same as well. The only difference is in the largest galaxies formed, which is directly proportional to σ_8 as it controls the clustering of mass. We note that the SFE is marginally higher than the abundance matching estimates for the lower mass halos, but the difference is $\lesssim 0.3$ dex. Further, the weak mass dependence of the global SFE trend is in agreement with zoom-in hydrodynamical simulations like FIREbox^{HR} (Feldmann et al. 2024).

3.1.2 21-cm signal from the IGM

We note that despite the disagreement in UVLFs for the four cosmological models shown in Figure 2a, the models still reproduce observable quantities such as the SFR and global SFE fairly well, as shown in Section 3.1.1. Further, they are broadly in agreement

with available data. We now look at IGM observables, and more specifically at the 21-cm signal power spectrum (calculated according to Equation 4), shown in Figure 7a at $z = 9$. At this redshift, we note from Figure 4 that the reionization history is primarily governed by the matter clustering. Thus, the σ_8 low model having the highest $\langle x_{\text{HI}} \rangle$ suggests significant contrasts between its large neutral and ionized regions, thus leading to a higher power amplitude up to $k = 0.40 \text{ h cMpc}^{-1}$ as compared to the other three models. On the other hand, greater matter clustering in the σ_8 high and h high models leads to lower contrast at these scales due to more numerous ionized regions, and thus less power. However, at smaller scales, having more ionized regions allows for greater contrast, and thus the h high model catches up with the fiducial model, and the σ_8 high model has the highest power overall at $k > 0.40 \text{ h cMpc}^{-1}$.

For a better understanding of the 21-cm signal power spectrum evolution, we additionally present its redshift dependence at large scales, i.e. $k = 0.15 \text{ h cMpc}^{-1}$ in Figure 8a. In particular, this allows us to compare how the 21-cm signal evolves across redshifts in the four cosmological models relevant to LOFAR observations. As

Figure 4. Redshift evolution of the average of the A and B-series volume-averaged neutral hydrogen fraction $\langle x_{\text{HI}} \rangle$ for the fiducial (cyan), h high (red), σ_8 low (purple) and σ_8 high (green) models for the unconstrained (top) and constrained (bottom) cases. Dotted lines refer to a fit to the curves, which is used for a better estimate of the redshift of reionization when the redshift resolution is too coarse. The vertical grey dashed lines indicate the observationally relevant redshifts for LOFAR ($z = 10.11, 9.16$ and 8.3), and the black solid line is drawn at $\langle x_{\text{HI}} \rangle = 0.5$ to guide the eye. Grey circles are a collection of observational constraints (Fan et al. 2006; Totani et al. 2006; Ota et al. 2008; Ouchi et al. 2010; Bolton et al. 2011; Dijkstra et al. 2011; McGreer et al. 2011; Mortlock et al. 2011; Ono et al. 2012; Chornock et al. 2013; Jensen et al. 2013; Robertson et al. 2013; Schroeder et al. 2013; Pentericci et al. 2014; Schenker et al. 2014; McGreer et al. 2015; Sobacchi & Mesinger 2015; Choudhury et al. 2015; Mesinger et al. 2015; Greig et al. 2017; Davies et al. 2018; Mason et al. 2018; Hoag et al. 2019; Greig et al. 2019; Jones et al. 2024, collected in the CoRECON module, Garaldi 2023).

suggested by the reionization histories, we note that the σ_8 low model has a larger contrast due to slower reionization, and thus has a higher amplitude of $\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2$ ($k = 0.15 \text{ h cMpc}^{-1}$) at the beginning of reionization. However, the σ_8 high and h high models overtake its amplitude due to the formation of larger ionized regions by $z \approx 8$.

3.2 Constrained case

As in this case, we have also changed parameters that control star formation efficiency and supernova feedback, it is crucial to understand their impact on observables other than the UVLFs shown in Figure 2b, which we analyze in the following subsections.

3.2.1 Galactic properties

As in Section 3.1.1, in Figure 5b we look at the A and B-series averaged SFMS and compare them with observations from JWST at $z = 10$ and 9 . We note that despite differences in the energy of supernovae (α_{SF} and $\alpha_{\text{SF,burst}}$ also differ for the σ_8 low model), the high mass ends of the SFMS of the four models still agree with each other and with observations. This is because the most massive galaxies are also the most luminous, and matching their UVLFs in Section 2.3 consequently matches their star formation properties. However, at the low-mass end, the SFMS of the four models shows

some deviation at both redshifts. This is because at lower masses, the impact of astrophysical parameters starts to dominate, and despite the σ_8 high model forming galaxies with masses smaller than the σ_8 low model, their median SFR is an order of magnitude smaller, because the energy released per supernova is high enough to clear out gas and suppress star formation in the low-mass galaxies.

To further explore the impact of the energy released by supernovae, in Figure 6b we also look at the global SFE. Here, we notice that, despite similar SFRs at the high-mass end, the efficiency of star formation in each case differs. The SFE for the σ_8 low model is significantly boosted compared to observations, while the fiducial and h high models only mildly overpredict the observed SFE. The σ_8 high case, on the other hand, is the best match. We note that the global SFE is inversely proportional to E_{SN} for all halo masses. The weak mass dependence trend of the SFE is the same of the unconstrained case, and in agreement with the trends of the FIREbox^{HR} simulations (Feldmann et al. 2024) for the fiducial, σ_8 high and h high models, while the σ_8 low model is an order of magnitude higher but with the same slope.

3.2.2 21-cm signal from the IGM

While the UVLFs at $M_{1600,\text{AB}} < -18$ in the constrained case are similar for all four cosmological models, the SFR and global SFE show differences, and in some cases do not match observations. In such a scenario, it becomes interesting to analyze the impact on the 21-cm signal. In Figure 7b, we present the 21-cm signal power spectrum at $z = 9$. Unlike the unconstrained case where the differences in matter clustering contributed to differences not only in the overdensity term but also in the neutral hydrogen fraction term in equation 2, here the changes in astrophysical parameters lead to a drastic reduction in the differences between the value of $\langle x_{\text{HI}} \rangle$ across the four models. Thus, the differences in the 21-cm signal power spectra of the four models are governed primarily by the overdensity term. This leads to a higher power across all wave modes for the σ_8 high model due to greater matter clustering. While one would expect the h high model to have slightly higher power than the fiducial one due to the dependence on overdensity, the neutral-fraction parameter reduces the contrast due to a marginally faster reionization process, so that the power in the two cases becomes similar. Even the σ_8 low model matches the fiducial and h high models' power spectra due to a faster reionization process.

In Figure 8b, we present the impact of the redshift evolution of the 21-cm signal power spectrum at $k = 0.15 \text{ h cMpc}^{-1}$ and notice a significant reduction in the differences of $\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2$ ($k = 0.15 \text{ h cMpc}^{-1}$) values between the various cosmological models at $12 > z > 5$ compared to the extent of differences in Figure 8a. Indeed, at $10 > z > 8.5$, where LOFAR observations have been made, variations in the σ_8 parameter lead to differences in the power spectrum of only a few mK^2 . While the exact magnitude of the difference is subject to the position of the peak of $\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2$ ($k = 0.15 \text{ h cMpc}^{-1}$), which in turn is governed by modeling assumptions like the choice of f_{esc} (see Appendix C for a comparison between $f_{\text{esc}} = 12.5\%$ and 25%), the key takeaway is that *significantly different choices of cosmological and astrophysical parameters can still lead to similar 21-cm signal observables, even when constrained by the UVLFs from JWST and HST observations*. Thus, for exploring the parameter space of acceptable models that agree with upper limits of 21-cm signal power spectra observations at LOFAR redshifts, one would still have to consider setting various cosmological and astrophysical parameters as free parameters.

 (a) Unconstrained case for redshifts $z = 10$ (top) and 9 (bottom).

 (b) Constrained case for redshifts $z = 10$ (top) and 9 (bottom).

Figure 5. Comparison of A and B-series averaged star formation rate (SFR) as a function of stellar mass for the unconstrained (left) and constrained (right) cases, for the fiducial (cyan), h high (red), σ_8 low (purple) and σ_8 high (green) models at redshifts $z = 10$ and 9. Solid lines refer to the median star formation rate in each mass bin, with 16th and 84th percentiles shown as shaded regions. Grey circles are observations from various JWST programs (Treu et al. 2023; Fujimoto et al. 2023; Looser et al. 2023; Bouwens et al. 2023b; Papovich et al. 2023; Arrabal Haro et al. 2023b,a; Long et al. 2023; Leethochawalit et al. 2023; Atek et al. 2023; Robertson et al. 2023; Heintz et al. 2023a,b; Jin et al. 2023; Helton et al. 2024; Jung et al. 2024).

 (a) Unconstrained case for redshifts $z = 10$ (top) and 9 (bottom).

 (b) Constrained case for redshifts $z = 10$ (top) and 9 (bottom).

Figure 6. Comparison of A and B-series averaged star formation efficiency (SFE) as a function of halo mass for the unconstrained (left) and constrained (right) cases, for the fiducial (cyan), h high (red), σ_8 low (purple) and σ_8 high (green) models at redshifts $z = 10$ and 9. Solid lines refer to the median SFE in each mass bin, with 16th and 84th percentiles shown as shaded regions. Grey circles are Spitzer observations from Stefanon et al. (2021), and grey triangles are abundance matching estimates from Tacchella et al. (2018).

4 DISCUSSION

By analyzing various galactic and IGM observables, we note that the interplay of astrophysical and cosmological parameters can lead to similarities as well as differences, even in the constrained case where the UVLFs of the four models agree with observations. For example, in the constrained case, while agreement with observed UVLFs leads to similar SFR for the high-mass galaxies across all

four models, there are significant deviations in the SFR for low-mass galaxies, as well as the global SFE.

For the IGM, we note that while the 21-cm signal power spectrum at the redshifts of interest is very similar across all four models in the constrained case as compared to the unconstrained case, this is due to the choice of astrophysical parameters, which reduces the impact of the cosmological parameters, producing similar reionization histories.

Figure 7. Comparison of A and B-series averaged normalized 21-cm signal power spectrum ($\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2$) for the unconstrained (left) and constrained (right) cases, for the fiducial (cyan), h high (red), σ_8 low (purple) and σ_8 high (green) models at redshifts $z = 9$.

Figure 8. Comparison of the redshift evolution of the A and B-series averaged normalized 21-cm signal power spectrum ($\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2$) at $k = 0.15 \text{ hcMpc}^{-1}$ for the unconstrained (left) and constrained (right) cases, for the fiducial (cyan), h high (red), σ_8 low (purple) and σ_8 high (green) models. The vertical dashed lines indicate the redshifts relevant for LOFAR, i.e. $z = 10.11, 9.16$, and 8.3 .

These similarities in terms of 21-cm observables have a profound impact on inference modeling, as models with very different cosmological and astrophysical parameters (which lead to different rates of reionization) can produce 21-cm signal power spectra in agreement with current upper limits (for example from [Mertens et al. 2020](#); [Trott et al. 2020](#); [HERA Collaboration et al. 2023](#)), or possibly also with an eventual measurement. This means that fixing any of these parameters could exclude viable models. While introducing cosmological and astrophysical parameters as free parameters during inference modeling has been attempted in several earlier studies (see e.g. [Kern et al. 2017](#); [Schneider et al. 2023](#)), these have used only approximate reionization simulation codes due to the significant computational costs involved in building such a high-dimensional parameter space. Indeed, in our setup, we would be required to run a large number of dark-matter only simulations with different cosmologies, each post-processed with a large set of astrophysical parameters. The problem worsens if one would like to boost the resolution of the simulations to take into account the role of mini halos (see [Haiman et al. 2001](#); [Iliev et al. 2005](#)) or dwarf galaxies ([Wu & Kravtsov 2024](#)), which likely play a significant role in the EoR. While one could use semi-numerical codes and emulators, they would not do a good job in

modeling galaxy-scale physics, nor in taking into account radiative transfer.

Because of this, boosting the resolution of low-resolution simulations using analytic techniques based on smaller boxes with higher resolution has been proposed (see for example [Nasirudin et al. 2020](#); [Barsode & Choudhury 2024](#)). Newer methods based on Machine Learning, such as using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs, as done in [Zhang et al. 2024](#)) bypass the requirement of a higher resolution simulation. However, it needs to be explored whether such methods are robust enough to factor in small differences in individual parameters. In subsequent work with POLAR, we intend to include resolution-boosting techniques to resolve halos and galaxies down by at least 2 orders of magnitude in mass.

The development and implementation of such techniques will additionally allow us to create more diverse training sets of power spectra for building Machine Learning kernels for Gaussian Process Regression based signal extraction, as shown by [Mertens et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Acharya et al. \(2024a,c\)](#).

5 SUMMARY

In this work, we have demonstrated the POLAR framework, which combines N -body dark matter only simulations using the GADGET-4 code with semi-analytic modeling of galaxies from L-GALAXIES, and 1-D radiative transfer employing GRIZZLY. We have applied the framework to four different cosmological models: a “fiducial” model, which adopts values of the cosmological parameters from Planck Collaboration et al. (2020); a “ h high” model, with $h = 0.733$ based on results from studies of Cepheid variables in the host galaxies of 42 Type Ia supernovae (Riess et al. 2022); a “ σ_8 low” case, with $\sigma_8 = 0.702$ from an anisotropic galaxy clustering measurement analysis done by Tröster et al. (2020); and a “ σ_8 high” case, with $\sigma_8 = 0.880$ according to recent eROSITA results (Ghirardini et al. 2024). We additionally used the Fixed & Paired approach (Angulo & Pontzen 2016) to suppress cosmic variance by boosting the effective volumes of the simulations. For all the quantities analyzed, we took an average of the fixed initial conditions case (which we refer to as the A-series) and its corresponding pair (referred to as the B-series).

We then chose astrophysical parameters in L-GALAXIES such that the fiducial model matches UV luminosity functions observed at $z = 10$ and 9 from HST legacy fields and JWST programs. To investigate the effect of adopting different values for h and σ_8 on other galactic and IGM observables, we use the same astrophysical parameters also for the other three cosmological models. We refer to this as the “unconstrained” case, as by not changing astrophysical parameters for the different cosmological models the resulting UVLFs will not necessarily be consistent with the observed ones. We also built a “constrained” case, where we instead choose the astrophysical parameters such that the UVLFs obtained in each cosmological model are consistent with those observed at $z = 10$ and 9. For this, we increased the star formation efficiency and reduced the energy released per supernova in the σ_8 low model to boost star formation and, in turn, its UVLF. On the other hand, we increased the energy released per supernova for the h high and σ_8 high models to suppress star formation and mitigate the impact of increased matter clustering as compared to the fiducial model. For the radiative transfer calculations, we only took into account the stellar sources while modeling the Spectral Energy Distributions (SEDs) and chose a global escape fraction of 12.5% across all redshifts for all four models.

Our results can be summarized as follows:

- **Reionization history:** In the unconstrained case, the values of the cosmological parameters strongly influence the matter clustering, which in turn leads to significant differences in how reionization progresses in each model. While the σ_8 high model reionizes by $z \approx 6.4$, the σ_8 low model is only 45% reionized even by $z = 5$. In the constrained case contrarily, the impact of astrophysical parameters is significant and the σ_8 low model reionizes the fastest by $z = 5.75$, while the σ_8 high model is only 70% reionized by $z = 5$.

- **Star Formation Rate (SFR):** In the unconstrained case, no significant differences are observed as the parameters controlling star formation have been kept the same. However, in the constrained case the SFR in low-mass galaxies is impacted by the required energy released per supernova, and thus the SFR is boosted for the σ_8 low model and suppressed for the σ_8 high model. In both cases, all models agree with observations at $z = 10$ and 9.

- **Global Star Formation Efficiency (SFE):** Due to the parameters controlling star formation being the same in the unconstrained case, the global SFE at all masses is the same across all four models. This is in agreement with observations and abundance matching estimates. However, in the constrained case, due to a higher value of the parameter regulating the star formation efficiency, the global

SFE in the σ_8 low model is also higher. The other three models show minor differences, governed by the differences in the energy released per supernova.

- **21-cm signal power spectrum:** In the unconstrained case, the differences between the four models are not only due to the difference in overdensity but also by those in the neutral fraction and its redshift evolution. However, in the constrained case, the neutral fraction at $z > 8$ is similar in all models, as the impact of matter clustering on the neutral fraction is canceled out by the impact of setting different values for the astrophysical parameters controlling star formation. Thus, the power spectrum at higher redshifts is mostly dictated by the overdensity term, and because of this it shows smaller differences among the four models.

Overall, we conclude that different values of cosmological and astrophysical parameters can lead to differences in some observables (e.g. low-mass SFR and global SFE), while others are unaffected (e.g. UVLFs and 21-cm signal power spectrum). In particular, we note that despite significantly different galactic processes and reionization histories, the 21-cm power spectra are very similar in power across k -bins and in agreement with current observational upper limits (Mertens et al. 2020; Trott et al. 2020; HERA Collaboration et al. 2023). Due to this, when doing inference modeling, it is essential to consider all cosmological and astrophysical parameters as free parameters, with other observed measurements serving as priors. While a limited exploration of astrophysical parameters can be done with excursion set algorithms, a Semi-Analytic Model provides a significantly more rigorous and physical approach to modeling galactic properties. For varying cosmological parameters though, it is necessary to run a large number of N -body simulations to populate the prior parameter space. However, running so many high-resolution simulations would be immensely expensive in terms of computational resources and time. To reduce the computational cost, we intend to incorporate techniques for boosting the resolution of less costly, low-resolution simulations using either analytic techniques or Machine Learning techniques in future work. This would still involve the running of a large number of N -body simulations, but having them run at a lower resolution can save on computational costs.

Implementation of this would also additionally allow us to build broader training sets of power spectra for the Machine Learning kernels used with Gaussian Process Regression by the LOFAR EoR Key Science Project team (as done by Acharya et al. 2024a).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

AA thanks the EoR research group at MPA, Volker Springel and Rüdiger Pakmor for helpful discussions. AA acknowledges Nordita’s PhD Fellows Visitor program for funding a part of this work, and thanks Nordita for their hospitality. Nordita is supported in part by NordForsk. RG acknowledges support from SERB, DST Ramanujan Fellowship no. RJF/2022/000141. GM is supported by the Swedish Research Council project grant 2020-04691_VR. SZ acknowledges the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation for the Humboldt Research Award and the Max Planck Institute for Astrophysics for its hospitality. The post-doctoral contract of IH was funded by Sorbonne Université in the framework of the Initiative Physique des Infinis (IDEX SUPER). LVEK acknowledges the financial support from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 884760, ‘CoDEX’).

This work used the color map “arctic” for slice images from the publicly available Python package CMASHER (van der Velden 2020)

and the Python package CoRECON (Garaldi 2023) for collating neutral fraction observations. Additionally, this work made extensive use of commonly used packages like NUMPY (Harris et al. 2020), MATPLOTLIB (Hunter 2007) and SciPY (Virtanen et al. 2020).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The simulation data, and post-analysis scripts used in this work can be shared upon reasonable request to the corresponding author.

REFERENCES

- Abdurashidova Z., et al., 2022, *ApJ*, 924, 51
- Acharya A., et al., 2024a, *MNRAS*, 527, 7835
- Acharya A., Garaldi E., Ciardi B., Ma Q.-b., 2024b, *MNRAS*, 529, 3793
- Acharya A., Mertens F., Ciardi B., Ghara R., Koopmans L. V. E., Zaroubi S., 2024c, *MNRAS*, 534, L30
- Adams N. J., et al., 2024, *ApJ*, 965, 169
- Anderson L., Pontzen A., Font-Ribera A., Villaescusa-Navarro F., Rogers K. K., Genel S., 2019, *ApJ*, 871, 144
- Angulo R. E., Pontzen A., 2016, *MNRAS*, 462, L1
- Arrabal Haro P., et al., 2023a, *Nature*, 622, 707
- Arrabal Haro P., et al., 2023b, *ApJ*, 951, L22
- Atek H., et al., 2023, *MNRAS*, 524, 5486
- Balu S., Greig B., Qiu Y., Power C., Qin Y., Mutch S., Wyithe J. S. B., 2023, *MNRAS*, 520, 3368
- Barrera M., et al., 2023, *MNRAS*, 525, 6312
- Barsode A., Choudhury T. R., 2024, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2407.10585
- Basu A., Garaldi E., Ciardi B., 2024, *MNRAS*, 532, 841
- Becker G. D., Bolton J. S., Madau P., Pettini M., Ryan-Weber E. V., Venemans B. P., 2015, *MNRAS*, 447, 3402
- Bhagwat A., Costa T., Ciardi B., Pakmor R., Garaldi E., 2024, *MNRAS*, 531, 3406
- Bird S., Ni Y., Di Matteo T., Croft R., Feng Y., Chen N., 2022, *MNRAS*, 512, 3703
- Bolton J. S., Haehnelt M. G., Warren S. J., Hewett P. C., Mortlock D. J., Venemans B. P., McMahon R. G., Simpson C., 2011, *MNRAS*, 416, L70
- Bosman S. E. I., et al., 2022, *MNRAS*, 514, 55
- Bouwens R. J., et al., 2015, *ApJ*, 803, 34
- Bouwens R. J., et al., 2021, *AJ*, 162, 47
- Bouwens R., Illingworth G., Oesch P., Stefanon M., Naidu R., van Leeuwen I., Magee D., 2023a, *MNRAS*, 523, 1009
- Bouwens R. J., et al., 2023b, *MNRAS*, 523, 1036
- Carniani S., et al., 2024, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2405.18485
- Casavecchia B., Maio U., Péroux C., Ciardi B., 2024, *A&A*, 689, A106
- Chartier N., Wandelt B., Akrami Y., Villaescusa-Navarro F., 2021, *MNRAS*, 503, 1897
- Chornock R., Berger E., Fox D. B., Lunnan R., Drout M. R., Fong W.-f., Laskar T., Roth K. C., 2013, *ApJ*, 774, 26
- Choudhury T. R., Puchwein E., Haehnelt M. G., Bolton J. S., 2015, *MNRAS*, 452, 261
- Choudhury M., et al., 2024, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2407.03523
- Ciardi B., Madau P., 2003, *ApJ*, 596, 1
- Davies F. B., et al., 2018, *ApJ*, 864, 142
- Dijkstra M., Mesinger A., Wyithe J. S. B., 2011, *MNRAS*, 414, 2139
- Dixon K. L., Iliev I. T., Mellema G., Ahn K., Shapiro P. R., 2016, *MNRAS*, 456, 3011
- Eide M. B., Graziani L., Ciardi B., Feng Y., Kakiichi K., Di Matteo T., 2018, *MNRAS*, 476, 1174
- Eide M. B., Ciardi B., Graziani L., Busch P., Feng Y., Di Matteo T., 2020, *MNRAS*, 498, 6083
- Esmerian C. J., Gnedin N. Y., 2021, *ApJ*, 910, 117
- Esmerian C. J., Gnedin N. Y., 2022, *ApJ*, 940, 74
- Esmerian C. J., Gnedin N. Y., 2024, *ApJ*, 968, 113
- Fan X., et al., 2006, *AJ*, 132, 117
- Feldmann R., et al., 2024, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2407.02674
- Field G. B., 1959, *ApJ*, 129, 551
- Finkelstein S. L., et al., 2015, *ApJ*, 810, 71
- Finlator K., Keating L., Oppenheimer B. D., Davé R., Zackrisson E., 2018, *MNRAS*, 480, 2628
- Fujimoto S., et al., 2023, *ApJ*, 949, L25
- Furlanetto S. R., Oh S. P., Pierpaoli E., 2006, *Phys. Rev. D*, 74, 103502
- Garaldi E., 2023, *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 8, 5407
- Garaldi E., Kannan R., Smith A., Springel V., Pakmor R., Vogelsberger M., Hernquist L., 2022, *MNRAS*, 512, 4909
- Garaldi E., et al., 2024, *MNRAS*, 530, 3765
- Georgiev I., Mellema G., Giri S. K., 2024, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2405.04273
- Ghara R., Choudhury T. R., Datta K. K., 2015, *MNRAS*, 447, 1806
- Ghara R., Mellema G., Giri S. K., Choudhury T. R., Datta K. K., Majumdar S., 2018, *MNRAS*, 476, 1741
- Ghara R., et al., 2020, *MNRAS*, 493, 4728
- Ghara R., et al., 2024, *A&A*, 687, A252
- Ghirardini V., et al., 2024, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2402.08458
- Giri S. K., Mellema G., 2021, *MNRAS*, 505, 1863
- Giri S. K., Mellema G., Aldheimer T., Dixon K. L., Iliev I. T., 2019a, *MNRAS*, 489, 1590
- Giri S. K., D'Aloisio A., Mellema G., Komatsu E., Ghara R., Majumdar S., 2019b, *J. Cosmology Astropart. Phys.*, 2019, 058
- Giri S. K., Schneider A., Maion F., Angulo R. E., 2023, *A&A*, 669, A6
- Giri S. K., Bianco M., Schaeffer T., Iliev I. T., Mellema G., Schneider A., 2024, *MNRAS*, 533, 2364
- Gnedin N. Y., 2014, *ApJ*, 793, 29
- Gnedin N. Y., Kaurov A. A., 2014, *ApJ*, 793, 30
- Greig B., Mesinger A., Haiman Z., Simcoe R. A., 2017, *MNRAS*, 466, 4239
- Greig B., Mesinger A., Bañados E., 2019, *MNRAS*, 484, 5094
- Greig B., Trott C. M., Barry N., Mutch S. J., Pindor B., Webster R. L., Wyithe J. S. B., 2021a, *MNRAS*, 500, 5322
- Greig B., et al., 2021b, *MNRAS*, 501, 1
- Greig B., Prelogović D., Qin Y., Ting Y.-S., Mesinger A., 2024, *MNRAS*, 533, 2530
- HERA Collaboration et al., 2023, *ApJ*, 945, 124
- Haiman Z., Abel T., Madau P., 2001, *ApJ*, 551, 599
- Han J., Cole S., Frenk C. S., Benitez-Llambay A., Helly J., 2018, *MNRAS*, 474, 604
- Harikane Y., et al., 2022, *ApJS*, 259, 20
- Harikane Y., et al., 2023, *ApJS*, 265, 5
- Harris C. R., et al., 2020, *Nature*, 585, 357
- Heintz K. E., et al., 2023a, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2306.00647
- Heintz K. E., et al., 2023b, *Nature Astronomy*, 7, 1517
- Helton J. M., et al., 2024, *ApJ*, 962, 124
- Henriques B. M. B., White S. D. M., Thomas P. A., Angulo R., Guo Q., Lemson G., Springel V., Overzier R., 2015, *MNRAS*, 451, 2663
- Henriques B. M. B., Yates R. M., Fu J., Guo Q., Kauffmann G., Srisawat C., Thomas P. A., White S. D. M., 2020, *MNRAS*, 491, 5795
- Hernández-Aguayo C., et al., 2023, *MNRAS*, 524, 2556
- Hirling P., Bianco M., Giri S. K., Iliev I. T., Mellema G., Kneib J. P., 2024, *Astronomy and Computing*, 48, 100861
- Hoag A., et al., 2019, *ApJ*, 878, 12
- Hogan C. J., Rees M. J., 1979, *MNRAS*, 188, 791
- Hothi I., Allys E., Semelin B., Boulanger F., 2024, *A&A*, 686, A212
- Hunter J. D., 2007, *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 9, 90
- Hutter A., Dayal P., Yepes G., Gottlöber S., Legrand L., Ucci G., 2021, *MNRAS*, 503, 3698
- Iliev I. T., Shapiro P. R., Raga A. C., 2005, *MNRAS*, 361, 405
- Iliev I. T., Mellema G., Ahn K., Shapiro P. R., Mao Y., Pen U.-L., 2014, *MNRAS*, 439, 725
- Jensen H., Laursen P., Mellema G., Iliev I. T., Sommer-Larsen J., Shapiro P. R., 2013, *MNRAS*, 428, 1366
- Jun S., et al., 2023, *A&A*, 670, L11
- Jones G. C., et al., 2024, arXiv e-prints, p. arXiv:2409.06405
- Jung I., et al., 2024, *ApJ*, 967, 73
- Kannan R., Garaldi E., Smith A., Pakmor R., Springel V., Vogelsberger M., Hernquist L., 2022, *MNRAS*, 511, 4005

- Kaur H. D., Gillet N., Mesinger A., 2020, *MNRAS*, **495**, 2354
- Kern N. S., Liu A., Parsons A. R., Mesinger A., Greig B., 2017, *ApJ*, **848**, 23
- Klypin A., Prada F., Byun J., 2020, *MNRAS*, **496**, 3862
- Koopmans L., et al., 2015, in *Advancing Astrophysics with the Square Kilometre Array (AASKA14)*. p. 1 ([arXiv:1505.07568](https://arxiv.org/abs/1505.07568)), doi:10.22323/1.215.0001
- Kostyuk I., Nelson D., Ciardi B., Glatzle M., Pillepich A., 2023, *MNRAS*, **521**, 3077
- Leethochawalit N., et al., 2023, *ApJ*, **942**, L26
- Leung G. C. K., et al., 2023, *ApJ*, **954**, L46
- Long A. S., et al., 2023, *arXiv e-prints*, p. [arXiv:2305.04662](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.04662)
- Looser T. J., et al., 2023, *arXiv e-prints*, p. [arXiv:2306.02470](https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.02470)
- Ma X., et al., 2018, *MNRAS*, **478**, 1694
- Ma Q.-B., Ciardi B., Eide M. B., Busch P., Mao Y., Zhi Q.-J., 2021, *ApJ*, **912**, 143
- Ma Q.-B., Ghara R., Ciardi B., Iliev I. T., Koopmans L. V. E., Mellema G., Mondal R., Zaroubi S., 2023, *MNRAS*, **522**, 3284
- Madau P., Meiksin A., Rees M. J., 1997, *ApJ*, **475**, 429
- Maio U., Péroux C., Ciardi B., 2022, *A&A*, **657**, A47
- Maion F., Angulo R. E., Zennaro M., 2022, *J. Cosmology Astropart. Phys.*, **2022**, 036
- Mason C. A., et al., 2018, *ApJ*, **857**, L11
- McGreer I. D., Mesinger A., Fan X., 2011, *MNRAS*, **415**, 3237
- McGreer I. D., Mesinger A., D'Odorico V., 2015, *MNRAS*, **447**, 499
- McLeod D. J., et al., 2024, *MNRAS*, **527**, 5004
- Mellema G., Iliev I. T., Alvarez M. A., Shapiro P. R., 2006, *New Astron.*, **11**, 374
- Mertens F. G., et al., 2020, *MNRAS*, **493**, 1662
- Mertens F. G., Bobin J., Carucci I. P., 2024, *MNRAS*, **527**, 3517
- Mesinger A., Furlanetto S., 2007, *ApJ*, **669**, 663
- Mesinger A., Furlanetto S., Cen R., 2011, *MNRAS*, **411**, 955
- Mesinger A., Aykutaalp A., Vanzella E., Pentericci L., Ferrara A., Dijkstra M., 2015, *MNRAS*, **446**, 566
- Molaro M., Davé R., Hassan S., Santos M. G., Finlator K., 2019, *MNRAS*, **489**, 5594
- Mondal R., Bharadwaj S., Majumdar S., 2017, *MNRAS*, **464**, 2992
- Mondal R., et al., 2020, *MNRAS*, **498**, 4178
- Mortlock D. J., et al., 2011, *Nature*, **474**, 616
- Murray S., 2014, HMF: Halo Mass Function calculator, *Astrophysics Source Code Library*, record ascl:1412.006
- Mutch S. J., Geil P. M., Poole G. B., Angel P. W., Duffy A. R., Mesinger A., Wyithe J. S. B., 2016, *MNRAS*, **462**, 250
- Nasirudin A., Iliev I. T., Ahn K., 2020, *MNRAS*, **494**, 3294
- Ocvirk P., et al., 2016, *MNRAS*, **463**, 1462
- Ocvirk P., et al., 2020, *MNRAS*, **496**, 4087
- Ono Y., et al., 2012, *ApJ*, **744**, 83
- Ota K., et al., 2008, *ApJ*, **677**, 12
- Ouchi M., et al., 2010, *ApJ*, **723**, 869
- Papovich C., et al., 2023, *ApJ*, **949**, L18
- Peacock J. A., 1999, *Cosmological Physics*
- Pentericci L., et al., 2014, *ApJ*, **793**, 113
- Planck Collaboration et al., 2020, *A&A*, **641**, A6
- Qin Y., Mesinger A., Bosman S. E. I., Viel M., 2021, *MNRAS*, **506**, 2390
- Riess A. G., et al., 2022, *ApJ*, **934**, L7
- Robertson B. E., et al., 2013, *ApJ*, **768**, 71
- Robertson B. E., et al., 2023, *Nature Astronomy*, **7**, 611
- Rosdahl J., et al., 2018, *MNRAS*, **479**, 994
- Santos M., Ferramacho L., Silva M., Amblard A., Cooray A., 2010a, SimFast21: Simulation of the Cosmological 21cm Signal, *Astrophysics Source Code Library*, record ascl:1010.025
- Santos M. G., Ferramacho L., Silva M. B., Amblard A., Cooray A., 2010b, *MNRAS*, **406**, 2421
- Saxena A., Cole A., Gazagnes S., Meerburg P. D., Weniger C., Witte S. J., 2023, *MNRAS*, **525**, 6097
- Schaeffer T., Giri S. K., Schneider A., 2023, *MNRAS*, **526**, 2942
- Schenker M. A., Ellis R. S., Konidaris N. P., Stark D. P., 2014, *ApJ*, **795**, 20
- Schneider A., Schaeffer T., Giri S. K., 2023, *Phys. Rev. D*, **108**, 043030
- Schroeder J., Mesinger A., Haiman Z., 2013, *MNRAS*, **428**, 3058
- Shaver P. A., Windhorst R. A., Madau P., de Bruyn A. G., 1999, *A&A*, **345**, 380
- Smith A., Kannan R., Garaldi E., Vogelsberger M., Pakmor R., Springel V., Hernquist L., 2022, *MNRAS*, **512**, 3243
- Sobacchi E., Mesinger A., 2015, *MNRAS*, **453**, 1843
- Springel V., White S. D. M., Tormen G., Kauffmann G., 2001, *MNRAS*, **328**, 726
- Springel V., Pakmor R., Zier O., Reinecke M., 2021, *MNRAS*, **506**, 2871
- Stanway E. R., Eldridge J. J., 2018, *MNRAS*, **479**, 75
- Stefanon M., Bouwens R. J., Labbé I., Illingworth G. D., Gonzalez V., Oesch P. A., 2021, *ApJ*, **922**, 29
- Tacchella S., Bose S., Conroy C., Eisenstein D. J., Johnson B. D., 2018, *ApJ*, **868**, 92
- Thomas R. M., et al., 2009, *MNRAS*, **393**, 32
- Tinker J., Kravtsov A. V., Klypin A., Abazajian K., Warren M., Yepes G., Gottlöber S., Holz D. E., 2008, *ApJ*, **688**, 709
- Totani T., Kawai N., Kosugi G., Aoki K., Yamada T., Iye M., Ohta K., Hattori T., 2006, *PASJ*, **58**, 485
- Tozzi P., Madau P., Meiksin A., Rees M. J., 2000, *ApJ*, **528**, 597
- Trac H., Chen N., Holst I., Alvarez M. A., Cen R., 2022, *ApJ*, **927**, 186
- Treu T., et al., 2023, *ApJ*, **942**, L28
- Tröster T., et al., 2020, *A&A*, **633**, L10
- Trott C. M., et al., 2020, *MNRAS*, **493**, 4711
- Vani A., Ayromlou M., Kauffmann G., Springel V., 2024, *arXiv e-prints*, p. [arXiv:2408.00824](https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.00824)
- Villaescusa-Navarro F., et al., 2018, *ApJ*, **867**, 137
- Virtanen P., et al., 2020, *Nature Methods*, **17**, 261
- Wu Z., Kravtsov A., 2024, *The Open Journal of Astrophysics*, **7**, 56
- Zaroubi S., 2013, *The Epoch of Reionization*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp 45–101, doi:10.1007/978-3-642-32362-1_2, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-32362-1_2
- Zhang X., Lachance P., Ni Y., Li Y., Croft R. A. C., Matteo T. D., Bird S., Feng Y., 2024, *MNRAS*, **528**, 281
- van der Velden E., 2020, *The Journal of Open Source Software*, **5**, 2004

APPENDIX A: UV LUMINOSITY FUNCTIONS ACROSS REDSHIFTS

As we tune the astrophysical parameters for the constrained case only to match the UVLFs at $z = 10$ and 9 , it is interesting to explore how the four cosmological models compare with the UVLFs at other redshifts. In Figure A1, we show results at redshifts $z = 12, 10, 9, 8, 7, 5$. We note that while the models mildly overestimate observational data at $z = 5$, this could be because astrophysical parameters may need to be evolved with redshift. Interestingly, the σ_8 low model tends to reproduce the bright end much better at lower redshifts.

Figure A1: As Figure 2a, but for the constrained case UVLFs at $z = 12, 10, 9, 8, 7$ and 5 .

APPENDIX B: δT_{B} MIDDLE SLICES

In Figure B1, we show the maps of δT_{b} of the B-series middle slices (the simulations with “paired” initial conditions in the F&P pair of simulations) for the four cosmological models in the constrained case at $z = 12, 10, 8,$ and 6 (from top to bottom). Here the darkest regions represent the ionized regions with $\delta T_{\text{b}} = 0$. Note that δT_{b} cannot assume negative values, due to the assumption of $T_{\text{S}} \gg T_{\text{CMB}}$.

Figure B1: Same as Figure 3 but for the B-series of simulations.

APPENDIX C: FIDUCIAL MODEL WITH $f_{\text{esc}} = 25\%$

In Figure C1, we show the average of the A and B-series volume-averaged neutral hydrogen fraction ($\langle x_{\text{HI}} \rangle$) versus redshift for an escape fraction of $f_{\text{esc}} = 12.5\%$ (cyan) and 25% (brown). We also show the 21-cm signal power spectrum ($\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2$) at $k = 0.15 \text{ hcMpc}^{-1}$ versus redshift in Figure C2 with the same colours. We note that as expected, a higher escape fraction leads to a faster rate of reionization, getting 50% reionized by $z \approx 7$ for $f_{\text{esc}} = 25\%$ as compared to $z \approx 6.4$ for $f_{\text{esc}} = 12.5\%$, which is where $\Delta_{21\text{cm}}^2 (k = 0.15 \text{ hcMpc}^{-1})$ also peaks.

Figure C1: As Figure 4, but for the fiducial model, for an escape fraction of $f_{\text{esc}} = 12.5\%$ (cyan) and 25% (brown).

Figure C2: As Figure 8, but for the fiducial model, for an escape fraction of $f_{\text{esc}} = 12.5\%$ (cyan) and 25% (brown).

This paper has been typeset from a \LaTeX file prepared by the author.